

agents used varies in the order of EDTA > Oxine > Cupferron > Dimethyl glyoxime. This may be due to the fact that the rock phosphates contain more calcium than other ingredients like aluminium, iron and magnesium.

This investigation clearly reveals that the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates increases in presence of complexing agents. As metal chelates are better source of micronutrient supply to plants^{7,8,9} rock phosphates with a small quantity of complexing agents are very useful for supplying micronutrient elements and phosphorus to plants.

References

1. D. C. GAMI, J. A. SANGHANIA and S. L. AGARWAL, Indian phosphate rock in fertilizer industry, FAI-ISMA Seminar, 1971, New Delhi Working Session No. 1, Paper No. 1, p. 8. Example cited in *Ind. J. Tech.*, 1979, 17, 65.
2. K. V. MATHEW, Developments in the design, engineering and fabrication of phosphoric acid plants in India, FAI-ISMA Seminar, 1971, New Delhi Working Session No. 2, Paper No. 2, 14 Example cited in *Ind. J. Tech.*, 1979, 17, 65.
3. S. C. K. VAID, *Fertil. News* 20 (Dec. 1975) 43.
4. A. HAJRA and S. N. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 516.
5. H. S. WASHINGTON, *Chemical Analysis of Rocks*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. New York, 10th Ed. 1930.
6. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Longmans Green & Co. London, 3rd Ed. 1961.
7. B. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 623.
8. N. S. RANDHAWA, Progress report of co-ordinated scheme of ICAR on micronutrients of soils for the year 1966-67, P.A.U. Hissar, India.
9. A. WALLACE, L. M. SHANNON, O. R. LUNT and R. D. IMPEY, *Soil. Sci.*, 1957, 84, 27.

Composition of Essential oil of *Elsholtzia strobilifera* Benth

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ELSHOLTZIA strobilifera Benth (N. O. Labiatae), a medicinal-aromatic species, possesses high content of essential oil. The oil has been found to possess antibacterial and antifungal properties^{1,2}. The light yellow coloured essential oil from the fresh plant material was extracted by steam distillation in 0.4% yield. The essential oil was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the physico-chemical properties determined by the conventional methods are: specific gravity = 0.9096/20°, ref. index = 1.4890/20°, sp. rota-

tion = + 4.1, acid value = 0.64, ester value = 13.79, ester value after acetylation = 49.9 and carbonyl value = 49.3.

The essential oil (100 ml) was first separated into hydrocarbon and oxygenated fractions by column chromatography⁴. These were then subjected to fractional distillation under reduced pressure (4-5 mm). Each fraction was purified by column chromatography using silica gel BDH (60-120 mesh) as adsorbent. Purity of the fractions was ascertained by TLC over silica gel coated plates in different solvent systems. In all eleven fractions were obtained and out of these 10 compounds were identified by preparing their characteristic derivatives⁵. The presence of β -pinene, α -phellandrene, dipentene, bisabolene, 1, 8-cineole, linalool, terpinen-4-ol, carvone, citronellol and geranyl acetate was established.

The major fraction (38%) gave tests for a keto compound (2,4-DNP, m.p. 146°). The IR spectrum gave strong bands at 3000, 2960-2910, 1720 and 1640 cm^{-1} , medium intensity bands at 1480, 1400, 1380, 1346, 1300, and 1070 cm^{-1} and weak bands at 840 and 610 cm^{-1} . The mass spectrum of the compound ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$) gave molecular ion peak at $m/e = 152$, the base peak at 55 and other prominent peaks at 40, 95, 83, 69 and 41. The structure is yet to be established with the help of PMR and C^{13} NMR.

TABLE—GLC OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *Elsholtzia strobilifera*

Peak No.	Relative retention time (dipentene=1)	Percentage in the oil	Compound identified
1	0.3	0.55	α -pinene
2	0.4	12.14	β -pinene
3	0.7	0.5	myrcene
4	0.8	1.8	α -phellandrene
5	1.0	10.4	dipentene
6	1.4	5.5	1,8-cineole
7	1.6	trace	γ -terpinene
8	1.8	0.15	<i>p</i> -cymene
9	2.5	1.9	linalool
10	3.0	trace	linalyl acetate
11	3.4	trace	bornyl acetate
12	4.2	trace	unidentified
13	4.4	3.5	terpinen-4-ol
14	4.8	10.5	carvone
15	5.0	38.0	unidentified ketone
16	6.0	4.8	bisabolene
17	6.6	4.4	citronellol
18	7.0	4.4	geranyl acetate

Gas-Liquid Chromatography :

The GLC of the oil was carried out using chromatograph equipped with thermal conductivity detector and 18 ft carbowax 20M (10%) column. The column and injection part temperatures were maintained at 160° and 200° respectively. Hydrogen was used as carrier gas (40 ml/min). Eighteen peaks obtained in the chromatogram were identified by comparing their relative retention times with those of the authentic samples recorded under identical operating conditions. The percentage of each constituent in the oil was determined by calculating corresponding peak areas. The results are given in the Table.

Thus GLC revealed the presence of seven more compounds, viz., α -pinene, myrcene, γ -terpinene, *p*-cymene, linalyl acetate, bornyl acetate and one unidentified compound in addition to those identified by chemical methods.

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References

1. N. D. MURARI and C. S. MATHELA, *Indian Perfumer*, 1978, XXII, 291.
2. N. D. MURARI and C. S. MATHELA, *Vet. Res. Bull.*, 1978, I, 24.
3. E. GUENTHER, "The Essential oils", Vol. I, D. Van Nostrand Col. Inc., N. Y. 1949.
4. J. G. KIRCHNER and J. M. MILLER, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1952, 44, 318.
5. E. GUENTHER, "The Essential Oils", Vol. II, D. Van Nostrand Co., New York, 1949.

Synthesis and Pharmacology of N-Substituted-4-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl) Piperidine-2,6-diones

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RECENTLY various N-substituted (alkyl, cyclo alkyl and aryl)-4-arylglutarimides have been reported to exhibit antineoplastic activity¹⁻⁷. Pyridine and pyrimidine bases are building blocks of nucleic acids and their various derivatives possess antitumor activity⁸. In view of these observations we synthesized N-heterocyclic-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2, 6-diones (IV) as possible antineoplastic agents. In these derivatives pyridine or pyrimidine residues may function as carrier groups. IVg was also prepared to incorporate glycine in the imide structure.

3-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl) glutaric acid (II), prepared by the reduction of corresponding glutaconic acid⁹ (I), was treated with Ac₂O to obtain the glutaric anhydride (III). Heterocyclic amines were condensed with III at

fusion temperature to furnish IVa-g. IR spectrum of IVd showed two peaks at 1690 and 1733 cm⁻¹ characteristic of cyclic imide structure.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on Gallenkamp m.p. apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectrum was recorded on Beckmann Acculab-10 Spectrometer.

(IVa) *N*-(4-Pyridyl)-4 (*p*-methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2,6-dione :

III (2.18g, 0.01M) and 4-amino pyridine (1.04g, 0.011M) were mixed and heated to 170-180° with stirring for 30 min. The residue was crystallized from water.

m.p. 163-164°. Yield : 1.6g (53%).

Anal : Found : C, 68.61 ; H, 5.28 ; N, 9.26%

Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₃ : C, 68.84 ; H, 5.43 ; N, 9.44%.

(IVg) 4-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl) piperidine-2, 6-dione-1-acetic acid :

III (2.18g, 0.01M) and glycine (0.75 g, 0.01M) were fused at 180-190° with stirring for 15 min. The dark residue was dissolved in NaHCO₃ solution, and filtered. The filtrate was neutralized with HCl and the regenerated solid was crystallized with water.

m.p. 167-168°. Yield : 2g (71.4%).

Anal : Found : C, 60.78 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 5.13%

Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₅NO₅ : C, 60.64 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 5.05%.

Pharmacology : Compounds IVc, b, d and e (NSC 301435-301438) were screened for anticancer activity *in vivo*. Compounds were injected i.p. in saline solution to male mice at doses 400, 200 and 100 mg/kg. The action of the compounds was observed by comparing the median survival time of control and test groups of animals (T/C%) in which P 388 lymphocytic leukemia was induced. The compounds failed to protect the animals from the growth of leukemia. No activity was indicated (% T/C > 140). No toxicity was also observed (as % T/C < 80 and no mortality). % T/C for these compounds are 100±5.